

D4.3 Report on the results of the mentoring programme scheme

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Information in this report that may influence other GEARING-Roles tasks

Linked Task	Points of Relevance
T4.3	Mentoring programme pilot for R2 female

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GEARING-Roles project

GEARING-Roles (Gender Equality Actions in Research Institutions to traNsform Gender ROLES) is a four-year (January 2019 – December 2022) Coordination and Support Action project (project number 1824536) that will bring together a pan-European group of academics and industry professionals to collaborate and exchange knowledge, good practices, and lessons learned on designing, implementing, and evaluating 6 Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). The project therefore has a firm objective of challenging and transforming gender roles and identities linked to professional careers and working towards real institutional change. This multidisciplinary, multinational, and multi-sectorial collaboration will be supported by training in this space, mentoring activities, awareness raising campaigns as well as bi-annual videos and podcasts and annual networking events.

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List of Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
UDEUSTO	Universidad de Deusto
IGOT-UL	Geographic Institute and Spatial Planning - University of Lisbon
UL	University of Ljubljana
SU	Sabancı University
OBU	Oxford Brookes University
ETAg	Estonian Research Council
FECYT	Fundación Española de Ciencia Y Tecnología (EURAXESS Spain Coordinators)
GEP	Gender Equality Plan

Executive Summary

This document summarizes the result of the mentoring programme FELISE (Feminst Leadership in Science), a common activity of all six gender equality plans (GEPs) within the GEARING Roles project. The report describes the design and implementation process, including the participant profiles, resources developed and activities organized during the programme.

1. Designing the mentoring programme

Mentoring concept

The design of the GEARING Roles mentoring programme was led by the Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology, FECYT, following the input from the gender equality plans (GEP) implementing partners:

- University of Deusto (ES), UDEUSTO
- Geographic Institute and Spatial Planning - University of Lisbon (PT), IGOT-UL
- Faculty of Arts of the University of Ljubljana (SI), UL
- Sabanci University (TR), SU
- Oxford Brookes University (UK), OBU
- Estonian Research Council (EE), ETAg

The basic elements of the programme agreed were:

Each GEP implementer should aim at securing 5 mentors and 5 mentees (ca. 30 participants in total)

By default, mentees would be early postdoctoral women researchers, while mentors would be senior (preferably) woman researchers, although some flexibility could be needed in order to fulfil the number of participants (e.g., including some PhD candidates as mentees if not enough postdoctoral researchers are available)

The programme would avoid the “fixing women” approach and aims at allowing the participants to:

1. Identify and critically discuss gendered norms and practices in academia to allow them to tackle gender inequalities at both individual and structural level.
2. Review the narrative within the institution and others to challenge gender-neutrality assumptions.
3. Experiment new work practices that will enable sustainable and meaningful careers.
4. Establish a network of peers supporting institutional change for gender equality.
5. Improve knowledge on academic career options and strengthen professional networks.

For the implementation, mentor-mentee pairs would be established within each of the institutions to focus their meetings around the topics of self-awareness; gender equality in research; barriers for women to develop a successful and satisfactory career; ideas on how to foster gender equality in research and teaching within the institution; and how the mentor can support the mentee in navigating the institutional culture and practices.

In addition, the interinstitutional scenario that the project offers would be used to reinforce FELISE with a sponsoring element. To the best of the existing possibilities, a match between mentors and mentees from different institutions based on similar research fields would be attempted to address issues about career advancement.

In summary, each senior feminist researcher participating in FELISE could act in a double capacity: as a mentor to a woman postdoctoral researcher from the same institution (intra-institutional mentoring pair), and as a sponsor of a woman post-doc from another institution from a similar research area (inter-institutional sponsoring pair), if a proper match was possible

Figure 1. Graphical representation of mentoring concept

FELISE – FEminist Leadership In ScienceE

The mentoring programme was branded as FELISE, standing for Feminist Leadership In ScienceE. A specific look and feel was agreed with all the partners to be used in the design of all the mentoring programmes resources and communication actions.

Figure 2. Banner of FELISE section in the GEARING Roles website presenting the programme (<https://gearingroles.eu/felise/>)

Implementation calendar

The final implementation calendar was as follows:

- Design of the programme: November 2019 – March 2020
- Preparing programme resources: January 2020 – April 2020
- Dissemination and recruitment of participants: May 2020 – June 2020
- Registration of participants and matching: June 2020
- Mentoring period: July 2020 – February 2021

2. Participants

Profiles

In line with the mentoring concept agreed among the programme coordinators and the GEP implementing partners, the following profiles were targeted to participate in the programme

Mentees:

- Early career women researchers working in the GEP implementing institutions
- Having the objective of pursuing an academic career
- With interest in learning and reflecting about the gender dimension of their career
- With willingness to foster institutional and individual changes to eliminate the barriers that hamper women progression in science
- Looking to be part of an international network of researchers supporting women in science

Mentors/sponsors:

- Senior researchers (tenured-track or permanent position) working in the GEP implementing institutions
- Having sensibility towards gender equality in research and teaching
- Wanting to contribute to supporting women in science career
- Interested in becoming an agent of change and learning more about how to foster institutional changes for achieving gender equality in academia
- Looking to be part of an international network of researchers supporting women in science

Securing participants

Each of the GEP implementing partners had the commitment of securing an average of 5 mentees and 5 mentors from within their institutions. In order to support this work a FELISE leaflet was prepared to facilitate dissemination. The leaflet was tailored for each of the institutions with specific contact information.

Figure 3. Content of the FELISE leaflets prepared for the GEP implementers providing an overview of the programme

Furthermore, several ad hoc “recruitment” webinars were delivered by FECYT along the month of June 2020 to clarify any doubts from potential participants.

Pairs established

Finally, altogether **70 researchers** were recruited to participate in the programme. This allowed establishing **35 inter-institutional mentoring pairs**:

- UDEUSTO: 9 pairs
- OBU : 6 pairs
- SU: 6 pairs
- ETAg: 5 pairs
- IGOT: 5 pairs
- UL: 4 pairs

GEP implementing partners were offered the possibility of proposing their own matches, although FECYT established a mandatory registration system to ensure that the necessary GDPR requirements were met for the communication needs along the programme, but also to collect information to do the mentoring matches if partners opted for this. Furthermore, this information was also used to establish the interinstitutional sponsoring pairs.

Figure 4. Registration system established by FECYT to meet GDPR requirements and complement the matching efforts of the GEP implementing partners.

Considering that the sample was restricted, the matching criteria for the sponsoring pairs were based on wide research domains as those applied in the European Research Council panels: Life Sciences (LS), Physical Sciences and Engineering (PE) and Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH). The following table summarizes this information per GEP implementing partner:

ROLES	Mentors / Sponsors			Mentees		
	LS	PE	SSH	LS	PE	SSH
Estonian Research Council (EE)	1	1	3	1	1	3
Oxford Brookes University (UK)	1	1	4	3	1	2
Sabancı University (TR)	0	3	3	0	4	2
University of Deusto (ES)	2	2	5	2	2	5
Geographic Institute and Spatial Planning – University of Lisbon (PT)	0	0	5	0	0	5
Faculty of Arts – University of Ljubljana (SI)	0	0	4	0	0	4

These numbers finally allowed proposing **33 interinstitutional sponsoring pairs** upon the launch of the mentoring period.

Mentee profiles

Based on the information compiled during the registration process, 80% of the mentees engaged in FELISE had never participated in a mentoring programme before, and those few who had, it was also as a mentee.

Slightly less than half of the mentees (46,67%) had participated previously in activities supporting gender equality including participating in other GEARING Roles actions, as well as other academic activities such as conferences, working in articles or campaigns for promoting scientific vocations for girls.

When questioned about formal training on gender equality issues in research and teaching, 40% informed of not having received any training, while 43,33% identified themselves as autodidacts. Almost 7% had gender equality as their research field.

In regards to the topics they were most interested in addressing during their participation in FELISE, the ranking was the following:

1. Ensure women’s full and effective participation and equal opportunities for leadership
2. Overcome discrimination at academic life
3. Strengthen sound initiatives for the promotion of gender equality
4. Enhance the use of enabling technology, in particular information and communication technologies, that allow girls and women to feel more informed, committed and autonomous
5. Prevent violence and harassment against women at universities and eliminate harmful practices for female students and staff
6. Introduce agents of change able to undertake reforms to give women equal rights

Mentor profiles

In the case of the mentors, more than 70% of the FELISE participants had no previous experience in mentoring programmes, and the majority of those who had, was also in the role of mentors.

Half of the mentors declared having participated in other activities supporting gender equality, most of them either connected to research activities or through trainings. Actually 66,7% of the mentors declared that their knowledge on gender equality was autodidact, while slightly more than 20%

acknowledged formal training on top of their research discipline and 12,50% declared that this was their research field.

In regards to management experience, 50% of the mentors mentioned current or previous management positions, although less than 40% of them included the management of gender equality issues.

In the case of mentors, the ranking of topics they were more interested in discussing during their participation in FELISE was the following:

1. Overcome discrimination at academic life
2. Ensure women's full and effective participation and equal opportunities for leadership
3. Introduce agents of change able to undertake reforms to give women equal rights
4. Strengthen sound initiatives for the promotion of gender equality
5. Prevent violence and harassment against women at universities and eliminate harmful practices for female students and staff
6. Enhance the use of enabling technology, in particular information and communication technologies, that allow girls and women to feel more informed, committed and autonomous

3. FELISE Resources

In order to support the mentoring and sponsoring relationships, several resources were prepared by the FELISE coordination team

FELISE Kick-off Meetings

To officially launch the FELISE mentoring period, two kick-off sessions were organized on June 30th 2020 and again on July 7th 2020 to facilitate the participation of all mentors and mentees. Apart from reminding the goals of the programme, these sessions allowed to insist on the commitments of the participants and on the definitions of mentoring and sponsoring relationships.

Participants commitments

- ✓ Respect
- ✓ Confidentiality
- ✓ Listen to each other and learn in the process
- ✓ Meet in person or virtually 7 times along 7 months (mentee will take the lead)
 - ✓ 5x Mentoring meetings
 - ✓ 2x Sponsoring meetings
- ✓ Fill a evaluation survey (beginning and end of the mentoring period).

- ✓ **Also, mentees:**
 - ✓ Fill the online post-meeting forms
 - ✓ Consider working on a personal career plan

What is mentoring?

- ✓ It's a **bidirectional relationship** where both can benefit
- ✓ It's about **sharing experiences, know-how and advice**
- ✓ **Open and continued dialogue** within the couple is the **main tool** in mentorship
- ✓ **Get to know one better** (strengths, weaknesses, etc.)
- ✓ Find ways to contribute to **institutional structural change**

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What is sponsoring?

- ✓ Sponsorship is defined as a **more influential relationship**
- ✓ Based on **common research fields** – sponsor/mentee match not confirmed!
- ✓ Offering **professional support**
- ✓ Fostering the implementation of specific actions to **advance in the professional career**
- ✓ Contributing to **professional networks**

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Figure 5. Slides used during the Kick-off meetings to ensure common understanding and managing expectations

FELISE Handbook

One of the key resources to support the meetings of the pairs the FELISE Handbook. This document which can be downloaded from the [GEARING Roles website](#) was designed to work as a guide for the programme. This included information on the basics of the programme, but more importantly proposed key topics to address during the pairs' meetings.

For the intra-institutional mentoring pairs, which were requested to meet at least 5 times, the following topics were proposed:

- **Organizational norms and practices:** Discussing the gender equality policy of the institution.

- **Narratives:** Reflecting on the academic career and existing gender inequalities
- **Transferable skills:** Analyzing the transferable skills acquired along a research career and identifying areas for improvement, particularly linked to take the role of “agent of change”.
- **Self-awareness:** Reflecting on career management issues, such as strengths and weaknesses or celebrating achievements.
- **Integrating gender perspective in teaching and research:** Discussing how to avoid gender biases in teaching and research.
- **Experimenting new practices:** Taking stock and translating insights into new professional behaviours.
- **COVID-19 and gender equality in research and teaching:** Exchanging personal experiences and discussing future implications in scientific careers

In the case of the inter-institutional sponsoring pairs, which were expected to have two meetings along the implementation period, the following topics could be addressed:

- **Career goals**
- **Professional networks**

Each of these topics proposed in the Handbook includes recommendations for previous thinking and reading, potential goals to achieve, and a set of questions that could be used to facilitate the conversation during the meeting. It is important to highlight though that these were only recommendations, and pairs had the possibility of addressing only some of the topics based on their interests and circumstances.

FELISE Career Development Template

Although not mandatory, FELISE mentees were invited to work on a career development plan with the mentor and/or sponsor. To facilitate this, another resource prepared for the participants, which is also available in the [GEARING Roles website](#), was a career development template to facilitate the definition of their mission, vision and values, as well as a reflection on competencies, achievements and actions needed. The template was also designed to facilitate the collection of information (e.g., professional contacts, events) which could stem from the relationship with the mentor and/or sponsor.

FELISE Trainings for mentees

Two capacity building sessions for the mentees were already planned during the design phase. In line with the objectives of the programme, the topics addressed in these trainings were the preparation of personal career development plans and a facilitated group reflection on academic careers. Both of these capacity building activities were implemented by [Vitae](#), a global leader in supporting the professional development of researchers, experienced in working with institutions as they strive for research excellence, innovation and impact.

The training *Professional development planning for researchers* introduced mentees to tools to manage their own professional development by practising a skills prioritisation and gaining practice in how to set objectives, reflect on progress, and provide evidence about professional competencies. It was organized on the 28th of October 2020 in two sessions to facilitate participation and 28 of the 35 mentees participated

A summary of the feedback provided by some of the participants (16) was:

- How would you rate this workshop overall? 14 Excellent, 2 Good

- How successful was the workshop in meeting your objectives? 13 Excellent, 3 Good
- Would you recommend the training? 16 Yes

The other capacity building activity was *Forum: Progressing in Academia*, a session focused on supporting women in academia in progressing their careers by providing a discussion forum in an open and positive environment, which enabled peer-learning and knowledge exchange whilst addressing a wide range of issues that women face in the management of their careers. This took place on the 18th of November 2020 also on two sessions to facilitate participation and 24 of the 35 mentees participated. A summary of the feedback provided by some of the participants (15) was:

- How would you rate this forum overall? 10 Excellent, 5 Good
- How successful was the forum in meeting your objectives? 8 Excellent, 6 Good, 1 Fair
- Would you recommend this forum to other researchers? 14 Yes, 1 Maybe

FELISE Keynote presentations

Along the mentoring period, the FELISE coordination team organized 3 webinars as part of the FELISE programme in order to support the engagement of the participants and to provide “food for thought” for their meetings. These were completely voluntary for the FELISE participants (mentees and mentors) and opened to a wider audience through the GEARING Roles consortium, EURAXESS, sister projects and social media (GEARING Roles Twitter account and FECYT Twitter account mainly):

Scientific communities to promote gender equality - Dr. Elena Gómez Díaz (Group Leader at IPBLN-CSIC) - 14 July 2020

- 87 people registered, 55 finally participated (20 FELISE participants)
- Feedback collected from 24 participants:
 - Please rate (1-5) how interesting this presentation was for you: 4,21
 - Please rate (1-5) how inspiring this presentation was to discuss gender inequality in research careers: 4,25

Mentoring as postdoc in Canada - Dr. Ruth Risueño (Group Leader at IJC & CSO at Leukos Biotech) – 4 November 2020

- 33 people registered, 25 finally participated (9 FELISE participants)
- Feedback collected from 9 participants:
 - Please rate (1-5) how interesting this presentation was for you: 3,89
 - Please rate (1-5) how inspiring this presentation was to discuss gender inequality in research careers: 3,78

You don't look like a scientist – Dr. Beatriz Maroto (Director of Operations in Amadix) – 4 December 2020

- 84 people registered, 41 finally participated (12 FELISE participants)
- Feedback from 21 participants:
 - Please rate (1-5) how interesting this presentation was for you: 4,14
 - Please rate (1-5) how inspiring this presentation was to discuss gender inequality in research careers: 4,04

Promotion of FELISE Mentoring Programme

Apart of disseminating the information about the open keynote presentations, at the time of preparing this report, the FELISE coordination team has presented the programme in:

- Eument-net Conference 2020 *Mentoring in Academia and Research: a Tool to Improve Gender Equality in Human Resource Management* (23 October 2020)
- EURAXESS BHO Meeting: Presentation to EURAXESS national coordinators in a session devoted to good practices in supporting researcher career development (18-19 November 2020)
- Community of Practice *STRATEGIES on Sustainable Gender Equality* meeting (12 January 2021)

4. Deviations from the initial design

This pilot mentoring programme was conceived as essentially virtual, especially due to the commitment to make use of the international environment facilitated by the GEARING Roles project. Assuming that this was a risk for the level of engagement of the researchers participating as mentors/sponsors and mentees, the programme included plans to organize an on-site a group mentoring session within the framework of the Second Annual GEARING-Roles Conference scheduled for Fall 2020. Unfortunately the restrictions caused by the COVID-19 pandemic obliged to having this conference on-line, and thus, the group mentoring session never took place. This situation was partially addressed through the topic of the second training for mentees, which took the form of a virtual forum to emulate a group mentoring session. Furthermore, a final wrap-up event was also organized by the FELISE Coordination team in collaboration with UDEUSTO on March 17th 2021 seeking an exchange of the FELISE experience between mentors and mentees.

Figure 6. Tweet of the FELISE Wrap-up meeting